

Derivation of statistical distribution laws without using calculus of variation and Lagrange undetermined multipliers

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Abstract : A different approach follows the derivation of three statistical distribution laws using Clausius inequality relation of second law of thermodynamics and Boltzmann entropy relation. This derivation avoids the calculus of variation and Lagrange undetermined multipliers. Following this method of derivation, an important thermodynamic property, chemical potential for all particles in the system, irrespective of their occupation of energy levels appears same and it is an outcome of the derivation.

Keywords : Entropy, Lagrange multipliers, chemical potential.

Introduction

From Boltzmann entropy relation, the derivation of three statistical distribution laws namely Maxwell-Boltzmann, Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac, use undetermined multipliers¹⁻⁴. The undetermined multipliers α and β are the requirements of calculus of variation to graft the conditions of constancy of number of particles and fixed amount of energy with the condition of maximum entropy at equilibrium. The introduction of Lagrange multipliers is mathematical requirement but their values and physical concepts become clear when the calculated quantities using statistical distribution and thermodynamic experimental results are compared.

The derivation of statistical distribution laws use calculus of variation and Lagrange multipliers along with the entropy maximum principle in a model system of N ideal gas atoms (particles) confined in a volume V having total energy E . The system is in a large heat reservoir to keep the constant temperature at T for small heat changes in the system. The N and E are,

$$N = \sum_i n_i \quad (1)$$

$$E = \sum_i n_i \varepsilon_i \quad (2)$$

where n_i is the number of particles in the i -th energy level

each having energy ε_i .

The entropy relation of Boltzmann is,

$$S = k \ln \Omega \quad (3)$$

The number of distinct arrangements or microstates Ω for indistinguishable particles is,

$$\Omega = \prod_i (g_i)^{n_i}/n_i! \quad (4)$$

where g_i is the degeneracy of i -th energy level and n_i is the number of particles occupying it at equilibrium and k is the Boltzmann constant. Using the Stirling's approximation, $\ln n! = n \ln n - n$, the entropy S of the system is,

$$\begin{aligned} S &= k \ln \Omega \\ &= k \ln \prod_i (g_i)^{n_i}/n_i! \\ &= k \sum_i n_i (\ln g_i/n_i + 1) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The conditions of entropy maximum, constant number of particles and the fixed amount of energy are as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} d \ln \Omega &= \sum_i \ln (g_i/n_i) dn_i \\ &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} dN &= \sum_i dn_i \\ &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$dE = \sum_i \varepsilon_i dn_i + \sum_i n_i d\varepsilon_i$$

the second summation in RHS represents the pressure-

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volume work which is zero at constant volume, hence for fixed amount energy,

$$dE = \sum_i \epsilon_i dn_i = 0 \quad (8)$$

Using Lagrange undetermined multipliers α and β the above three conditions are combined in a single equation as,

$$\sum_i (\ln (g_i/n_i) - \beta \epsilon_i + \alpha) dn_i = 0 \quad (9)$$

All dn_i depend on each other because of the conditions (1) and (2). Several authors^{5,6} pointed out that the method of Lagrange multipliers guarantees that each term in the equation can be put individually and independently equal to zero, providing that variation parameters are finally chosen so as to satisfy these two auxiliary conditions of (1) and (2).

Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in terms of α and β is,

$$n_i = \exp (\alpha) g_i \exp (-\beta \epsilon_i) \quad (10)$$

The constant α is evaluated using condition (1) of constant number of particles in the system but the evaluation β requires the comparison of thermodynamic results and is evaluated as $(1/kT)$.

Different approach

There are a few attempts to avoid mathematical abstractness of the Lagrange undetermined multipliers and several such attempts use the minimization of Helmholtz energy⁷⁻⁹ at equilibrium but the concept of Helmholtz energy and its minimization depend on the thermodynamic entropy and its maximization at equilibrium. In this attempt, we avoid the condition of entropy maximum at equilibrium and Lagrange multipliers to derive three statistical distributions using Boltzmann entropy relation and Clausius inequality relation of entropy change. The Clausius inequality relation of entropy change is the basis of second law of thermodynamics, which is

$$q/T \leq \Delta S \quad (11)$$

where q is heat absorbed by the system at temperature T and ΔS is the entropy change in the process. The equality sign is applicable for the reversible or quasi-static processes, in which the system always remains at equilibrium.

$$q_{\text{rev}} = T\Delta S \quad (12)$$

From the first law of thermodynamics, we have

$$\Delta U = q + w \quad (13)$$

Here ΔU is the internal energy change due to absorption of heat q at temperature T and w is the work done on the system. In a reversible process,

$$\Delta U = T\Delta S + w_{\text{rev}} \quad (14)$$

For a reversible process at constant volume, w_{rev} is zero and the change of internal energy is equal to $T\Delta S$. In this process the entropy change is,

$$\Delta U/T = \Delta S \quad (15)$$

Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution

A model system is considered at equilibrium containing N particles in volume V and at temperature T . From (5), the change of entropy in a reversible process if a particle moves from p -th energy level to q -th energy level is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S &= k \ln \Pi_{i \neq p,q} (g_i)^{n_i}/n_i! \cdot (g_p)^{n_p-1}/(n_p-1)! \cdot (g_q)^{n_q+1}/(n_q+1)! - k \ln \Pi_i (g_i)^{n_i}/n_i! \\ &= k \ln (g_q/(n_q+1)) \cdot (n_p/g_p) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

In the process of moving a particle from p -th energy level to q -th energy level, the system absorbs heat to increase the internal energy of amount

$$\Delta U = \epsilon_q - \epsilon_p \quad (17)$$

And the entropy change due to heat absorption using (15) is,

$$\Delta S = (\epsilon_q - \epsilon_p)/T \quad (18)$$

Equating (16) and (18) we get,

$$(\epsilon_q - \epsilon_p) = kT \ln (g_q/(n_q+1)) \cdot (n_p/g_p)$$

Which on rearrangement gives,

$$\epsilon_q - kT \ln (g_q/(n_q+1)) = \epsilon_p - kT \ln (g_p/n_p) \quad (19)$$

as

$$n_q \gg 1, \epsilon_q - kT \ln (g_q/n_q) = \epsilon_p - kT \ln (g_p/n_p) \quad (20)$$

Any statistical approach is valid only if the numbers n_q 's are very large and in the energy level where the numbers are small, their contribution in the ultimate result should be small for any statistical approach.

The dummy indices p and q in (20) are applicable to any two indices p and i or i and j and so on. The expression for energy level of RHS of (20) is independent of the energy level of the LHS, hence they must be equal to a quantity μ' which is independent of the energy level.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \varepsilon_i - kT \ln (g_i/n_i) \\
 & = \varepsilon_j - kT \ln (g_j/n_j) \\
 & = \varepsilon_p - kT \ln (g_p/n_p) \\
 & = \dots\dots \\
 & = \mu'
 \end{aligned} \tag{21}$$

Rearranging we get,

$$\begin{aligned}
 & g_i \exp (-\varepsilon_i/kT)/n_i \\
 & = g_j \exp (-\varepsilon_j/kT)/n_j \\
 & = \dots\dots\dots \\
 & = \exp (-\mu'/kT)
 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

The Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution is given as,

$$n_i = \exp (\mu'/kT) g_i \exp (-\varepsilon_i/kT) \tag{23}$$

Using (1) and (23) we have,

$$\begin{aligned}
 N \exp (-\mu'/kT) & = \sum_i g_i \exp (-\varepsilon_i/kT) \\
 & = z
 \end{aligned} \tag{24}$$

The quantity z is the partition function of the system and Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution (23) becomes,

$$n_i = (N/z) g_i \exp (-\varepsilon_i/kT) \tag{25}$$

The n_i is the number of particles in i -th energy level of degeneracy g_i . At constant temperature T , putting ($\mu'/kT = \alpha$), we get the familiar form of Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution law from (23),

$$n_i = \exp (\alpha) g_i \exp (-\varepsilon_i/kT) \tag{26}$$

Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac statistics

Let at equilibrium the number of distinct arrangements of indistinguishable bosons is,

$$\Omega_{BE} = \prod_i (g_i + n_i - 1)/(g_i - 1)! n_i! \tag{27}$$

On moving a boson particle from p -th energy level to q -th energy level, the change of entropy is

$$\Delta S_{BE} = k \ln (g_q + n_q)/(n_q + 1) \cdot (n_p)/(g_p + n_p - 1)$$

As before we may use the conditions, n_p and $n_q \gg 1$

$$\Delta S_{BE} = k \ln (g_q + n_q)/n_q \cdot (n_p)/(g_p + n_p) \tag{28}$$

From (18) and (28), we get the relation,

$$\varepsilon_q - kT \ln (g_q + n_q)/n_q = \varepsilon_p - kT \ln (g_p + n_p)/n_p \tag{29}$$

as we have proceeded previously in MB statistics,

$$n_i = g_i/(\exp (-\alpha) \exp (\varepsilon_i/kT) - 1) \tag{30}$$

In the case of Fermi-Dirac statistics,

$$\Omega_{FD} = \prod_i g_i!/(g_i - n_i)! n_i! \tag{31}$$

The change of entropy with the moving of a fermion from p -th to q -th energy level is,

$$\Delta S_{FD} = k \ln ((g_q - n_q)/n_q) \cdot (n_p)/(g_p - n_p) \tag{32}$$

As before we get, the Fermi-Dirac distribution as

$$n_j = g_j/(\exp (-\alpha) \exp (\varepsilon_j/kT) + 1) \tag{33}$$

Chemical potential

The Helmholtz energy¹⁰ A is expressed as,

$$A = E - TS \tag{34}$$

where E is the internal energy of the system at temperature T and volume V with entropy S .

From (2) and (5),

$$A = \sum_i n_i \varepsilon_i - kT \sum_i n_i (\ln (g_i/n_i) + 1) \tag{35}$$

The Helmholtz energy per particle in i -th energy level is,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\partial A/\partial n_i)_{T,V} & = \varepsilon_i - kT \ln g_i/n_i \\
 & = -kT \ln (g_i/n_i) \exp (-\varepsilon_i/kT), \text{ from (21)} \\
 & = \mu'
 \end{aligned} \tag{36}$$

And from (24) $\mu' = -kT \ln z/N$

From (21), we also know, the above partial derivative does not depend on the subscript i or j . We may express,

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\partial A/\partial n_i)_{T,V} & = (\partial A/\partial n_j)_{T,V} \\
 & = (\partial A/\partial n_k)_{T,V} \\
 & = \dots \\
 & = (\partial A/\partial N)_{T,V}
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 A & = \int (\partial A/\partial N)_{T,V} dN \\
 & = \int (-kT \ln z/N) dN \\
 & = -kT \ln z^N/N!
 \end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

The Helmholtz energy per mole of particles at constant temperature T and constant volume V is known as chemical potential so the parameter (α) of all statistical distribution functions in (26) for Maxwell-Boltzmann, in (30) for Bose-Einstein and in (33) for Fermi-Dirac statistics are related to chemical potential per particle. The (α) is the Helmholtz energy or chemical potential per particle in units of (kT). From eqs. (23) and (25), we can get the Helmholtz energy per particle in a familiar form as,

$$\mu' = kT \ln N/z \tag{38}$$

where N/z is the effective concentration of particles.

Maximum entropy and minimum Helmholtz energy at equilibrium

As we have not follow the method of calculus of variation or do not use the Lagrange undetermined multipliers and we have not used the entropy maximum condition at equilibrium. Using the Clausius and Boltzmann entropy relations, we arrived at the condition of equilibrium distribution of particles in eq. (22). We have to check whether this distribution supports entropy maximum and Helmholtz energy minimum at equilibrium. Let us consider a process in which total energy, total number of particles and volume of the system remains constant at temperature T changing only the particle distribution or the entropy. If one particle moves from p -th level to q -th level and another particle moves from r -th level to s -th level such that,

$$(\epsilon_q - \epsilon_p) + (\epsilon_s - \epsilon_r) = 0 \quad (39)$$

The entropy change in the process, keeping energy and number of particles constant, is

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta S &= k \ln \Pi_{i \neq p,q,r,s} (g_i)^{n_i}/n_i! \cdot (g_p)^{n_p-1}/(n_p-1)! \cdot \\ &\quad (g_q)^{n_q+1}/(n_q+1)! \cdot (g_r)^{n_r-1}/(n_r-1)! \cdot \\ &\quad (g_s)^{n_s+1}/(n_s+1)! - k \ln \Pi_i (g_i)^{n_i}/n_i! \\ &= k \ln (g_q/n_q) \cdot (n_p/g_p) \cdot (g_s/n_s) \cdot (n_r/g_r) \\ &= k \ln (g_q/n_q) \cdot (n_p/g_p) \cdot (g_s/n_s) \cdot (n_r/g_r) \\ &\quad + k \ln (n_q/(n_q+1)) \cdot (n_s/(n_s+1)) \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

From (22) and (39),

$$\begin{aligned} &(g_q/n_q) \cdot (n_p/g_p) \cdot (g_s/n_s) \cdot (n_r/g_r) \\ &= \exp((\epsilon_q - \epsilon_p) - (\epsilon_s - \epsilon_r)) \\ &= 1 \\ \Delta S &= k \ln (n_q/(n_q+1)) \cdot (n_s/(n_s+1)) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

as the product $(n_q/(n_q+1)) \cdot (n_s/(n_s+1))$ is a fraction, its logarithm is less than zero, hence any deviation from equilibrium distribution, the entropy change is negative which is the condition of entropy maximum at equilibrium.

The change of Helmholtz energy at constant temperature and volume V can be calculated using (41) and the internal energy change from (39) as,

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta E &= (\epsilon_q - \epsilon_p) - (\epsilon_s - \epsilon_r) = 0, \\ \Delta A &= \Delta E - T\Delta S \\ &= -kT \ln (n_q/(n_q+1)) \cdot (n_s/(n_s+1)) > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

The deviation from equilibrium distribution produces positive change in Helmholtz energy, hence at equilibrium Helmholtz energy is minimum.

Conclusion

The approach of deriving the statistical distribution laws using Clausius inequality relation of second law of thermodynamics and Boltzmann relation of entropy avoids the assumption of entropy maximum at equilibrium and does not require to introduce mathematically abstract Lagrange undetermined multipliers. The distribution obtained is enough to show the maximum of entropy and the minimum of Helmholtz energy at equilibrium. The most important is that this derivation automatically arrives at the quantity known as the Helmholtz energy per particle. This is not an obvious outcome of the approach using the calculus of variation and Lagrange undetermined multipliers.

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References

1. T. L. Hill, "Introduction to Statistical Thermodynamics", Addison-Wesley Publishing Co. Inc., Reading, Massachusetts, 1960, pp. 10-12, 22.
2. R. K. Pathria, "Statistical Mechanics", 2nd ed., Butterworth Heinemann Linacre House, Oxford, 1996, pp. 129.
3. P. W. Atkins, "Physical Chemistry", 6th ed., Oxford University Press, Oxford, Melbourne, Tokyo, 1998, pp. 572-573.
4. Max. Born, "Atomic Physics", 7th ed., Blackie & Sons Limited, London, 1963, p. 428.
5. H. B. Callen, "Thermodynamics and an Introduction to Thermostatistics", 2nd ed., John Wiley and Sons, Inc., 1985, pp. 383.
6. D. A. McQuarrie, "Statistical Mechanics", 1st Indian ed., Viva books Private Ltd., New Delhi, Mumbai, Chennai, Kolkata, 2003, p. 40.
7. F. T. Wall, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci. USA*, 1971, **68**, 1720.
8. C. W. David, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 2006, **93**, 1695.
9. D. K. Russell, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1996, **73**, 299.
10. K. Denbigh, "The Principles of Chemical Equilibrium", 3rd ed., Cambridge at the University Press, 1971, p. 80.